

Exploring Modality in 19th-Century Diplomatic Treaties: A Parser-based Linguistic Analysis of the Burney, Robert, and Bowring Treaties between Siam (now Thailand) and Western Powers

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Abstract

This project aims to analyze modal verb phrases (modal verb + infinitive verb) in three different treaties: Burney, Robert, and Bowring Treaties different in their objectives and periods of time. Modal verbs like *shall*, *should*, *can*, or *could* convey different attitudes, and in the discourse of international relations and politics, modal verbs can reveal hidden intentions and underlying power dynamics. Although the three diplomatic treaties have been well-studied in terms of their societal, political, and economical consequences, this linguistic arena on the use of modal verbs has been underexplored. This study attempts to answer the following research questions: i) what are the most common modal verb phrases used in the three treaties? ii) what do the modal verb phrases represent? and iii) how do the occurrence frequencies compare between the three treaties and over time?

A combination of qualitative and quantitative methods and tools is implemented. While the Burney and the Bowring Treaties can be downloaded from Wikisource, the Roberts Treaty needs to be digitized. Therefore, the study also employs Transkribus as a digitization image-to-text tool. To process the treaty texts, a text parser spaCy is used to extract the modal verb phrases. A set of nine modal verbs is used as keywords together with the dependency tag “aux” to identify the modal verb phrases. The context words in the same sentence of modal verb phrases are also extracted into sub-corpora for further analysis. The occurrences of modal verb phrases are counted and categorized based on Someya’s 13 categorization (2010). The significance of the phrases are evaluated using frequency analysis, O/E score, t-score, and p-value. Semantic shift analysis is conducted based on Millar’s framework of epistemic and deontic sense (2009). Close-reading, semantic map, and Critical Discourse Analysis (CDA) are also employed for a local scale analysis.

1. Introduction

In the 19th century, the Kingdom of Siam (now Thailand) faced an expanding influence of the Western powers. With other major countries like China and Myanmar having a brutal conflict during this encounter, Siam chose a more compromising way, making a pact. Therefore, this period brought about three pivotal treaties: the Burney Treaty of 1826 between Siam and Great Britain, the Robert Treaty of 1833 between Siam and the United States, and the Bowring Treaty of 1855 between Siam and Great Britain. These agreements aimed to facilitate trade and establish diplomatic relations between Siam and Western powers. While these treaties are well-documented for their historical significance, their linguistic aspects, particularly the use of modal verbs, remain relatively unexplored.

This project seeks to address this gap by conducting a comparative linguistic analysis of modal verbs in the Burney, Robert, and Bowring Treaties. Modality refers to the ways of using linguistic mechanisms to express different attitudes. Modality verbs, such as *can*, *must*, *should*, or *may*, can indicate various degrees of certainty, obligation, permission, ability, necessity, and possibility. Modal verbs play an essential role in diplomatic discourse, revealing the intention and interpretation of treaties. By examining modal verbs in these treaties, the study can provide valuable insights into the linguistic strategies employed by diplomats, the cultural nuances of diplomatic communication, and the pragmatic functions served by the use of modal verbs in cross-cultural contexts.

2. Background Theory and Framework

2.1. Previous studies

Numerous studies have been conducted on the impacts of the treaties on society, politics, economy, and even the agricultural environment of Siam; however, very few have analyzed the treaties' texts using a linguistic framework. In terms of modality, many studies and essays (e.g. Meethong et al. 2020; Trisadikoon 2021) reflect a local perspective pointing out that the treaties imposed obligations on Siam opposing an amicable relationship as the names suggest. Other studies (e.g. Nucharee & Smith 2019; Terwiel 1991) provide a more balanced view criticizing British optimism while also considering the reality from the Siamese side. Both groups of studies, despite the fact that they do not involve linguistic examination of the treaties, project a different degree of obligatory nature of the treaties.

In terms of the studies that use a text parser under a linguistic framework, most studies are conducted at a global scale of the whole language and with a focus on the parser's performance, e.g. examining syntactic features of the New Englishes (Schneider 2009), examining verb-particle constructions in the Wall Street Journal corpus (WSJ) (Baldwin & Villavicencio 2002), and extracting collocations across multiple languages (Seretan & Wehrli 2006). Surprisingly, not many studies employ a text parser in linguistic analysis. One of such studies is the exploration of subject-verb and verb-object relations in active and passive constructions by Lehmann and Schneider (2009). Even more surprisingly, a parser applied in linguistic analysis is found in a medical field. Such studies include the identification of the terms related to biomedical events (Rinaldi et al. 2007; MacKinlay et al. 2011), and negation constructions in biomedical texts (Sohn et al 2012). For the use of a parser with historical texts, most literature is geared towards computational aspects aiming to improve a parser's performance in handling such datasets (e.g. Schneider 2012; Rayson et al. 2007).

This study is, therefore, one of its kind to utilize a state-of-art text parser, spaCy, on historical texts to answer linguistic research questions.

2.2. Modality

The two studies that provide a useful framework for this project in terms of the categorization and the semantic shift of modal verbs are those of Someya (2010) and Millar (2009). Someya analyzed nine major modal verbs (will, would, can, shall, should, may, must, could, and might) in the Business Letter Corpus (BLC). Based on the three common categories of modal verbs: possibility modals (can, may, might, could), necessity modals (ought, should, must), and predictive modals (will, would, shall), together with Coates' categorization (1983): obligation, inference, hypothesis, quasi-subjunctive, possibility, ability, permission, and volition, Someya came up with 13 categories. Dividing the meanings of modal verbs into primary, secondary, and tertiary, Someya concluded that the use of modal verbs tend to be skewed towards the primary meaning as illustrated in the table below. The study also points out that *should* is the most complex modal verb semantically with 6 possible interpretations. Even though the dataset is different in nature with the treaty project, this study provides a comprehensive categorization of modal verbs.

Semantic Functions (F1 ~ 13) *	will	shall	would	might	could	can	may	should	must
F1. OBLIGATION / NECESSITY		25.4							79.6
F2. STRONG SUGGESTION								65.5	
F3. CONFIDENT INFERENCE								15.4	20
F4. TENTATIVE INFERENCE				9.2			85		
F5. REAL POSSIBILITY					3.7	77.5			
F6. ABILITY					4.2	20			
F7. PERMISSION						2.1	13.3		
F8. VOLITION	47.1	63.3	1.7						
F9. SIMPLE FUTURE PREDICTION	52.9	11.3	0.8						
F10. HYPOTHESIS MARKER			27.1	71.3	79.2			12.5	
F11. POLITENESS MARKER			70	19.6	12.9			5	
F12. DEONTIC SUBJUNCTIVE								0.8	
F13. OTHERS			0.4			0.4	1.7	0.8	0.4
TOTAL (%)	100	100	100	100	100	100	100	100	100

Distribution of the major semantic functions of modals in the BLC (Someya 2010)

To take into account the shift in meanings of modal verbs, the study of Millar (2009) can be useful. Millar tracked semantic changes of the modal verbs *may*, *should* and *must* to be comparable with Leech (2003). The senses in the analysis include epistemic and deontic. Epistemic sense includes possibility, probability, and certainty while deontic sense mainly involves permission, obligation, and necessity. Millar took a random sample from the years 1923, 1960, and 2000 and found the same patterns with Leech as *may* shifted towards epistemic sense, *should* to the root meaning of weak obligation, and *must* from deontic to epistemic sense. Millar's project harnesses the benefit of the TIME Corpus being a large corpus of more than 100 million words and a long time-span of over 70 years, but the section dedicated to semantic analysis is concise and incomprehensive analyzing only 3 modal verbs within a randomly sampled dataset.

2.3. Treaties

During the Industrial Revolution (1760-1850), the western powers, especially Great Britain, sought commercial competitiveness and intended to establish a fairer trade relationship with Siam. In Siam (former Thailand), international businesses were conducted through the Treasury. In other words, there were no direct contacts between local and foreign business

entities. Great Britain desired to develop a free-trade relationship in order to gain more resources for the colonies, especially India. The wish list included rice, wood, and tin. The following background story, especially about the Bowring Treaty, which is considered the most canonical treaty that opened up Siam economically, politically, and culturally, is narrated in detail in order to set the stage of the significance of the treaty, and above all, portray the circumstances in which the treaty was written and signed. The insightful historical backdrop of the Bowney Treaty is based on a historian featured in the FAROSE podcast's channel People You May Know (2022).

2.3.1. The Bowring Treaty (1855)

The cover of the Bowring Treaty

<https://youtu.be/TpAQoEllpss?si=Av4AGTLPIyK30ybV>

The Bowring Treaty was named after Sir John Bowring, who played a crucial role in the agreement. Sir John Bowring favors free trade believing free trade will liberate people from obligations and uplift their well-being. He was the owner of the famous quote “free trade is Jesus Christ.” After getting into politics in Great Britain, he was sent to Asia and became the fourth governor of Hong Kong. Great Britain made several attempts in negotiating trade with

Siam without success. The Burney Treaty previously achieved was not liberal and had too many restrictions. Sir James Brooke who governed India at that time left Siam with empty hands, so he left with a letter to the Great Britain government recommending that the next negotiation should be accompanied by a fleet. The negotiation assignment was transferred to Sir John Bowring, who got familiarized with traditions and customs of Siam. He pointed out that title and authority were a crucial factor in successful negotiation. He was, later, appointed the ambassador of Queen Victoria to negotiate with Siam.

Siam heard the news about the visit and proactively made a contact asking about the details of the visit including date, number of people, and content of the treaty to prepare for the reception and facilitate the negotiation. Great Britain brought two fleets which were allowed to enter the land and anchored near the house of a senior nobleman who prepared the reception. King Rama IV appointed five plenipotentiaries who had full powers in Siam for the negotiation (Bowring Treaty 2022): one was his brother, two controlled the army and the civilian, one took care of the western and the southern ports, and one took care of the eastern ports. His brother and the last two representatives were liberal and optimistic with the trade agreement while the other two were reluctant to comply. However, in general, everyone including the King knew, with the defeat of China and Myanmar in mind, that the agreement had to be achieved. The treaty was signed within just a week.

The Bowring Treaty consisted of 21 points outlining the agreement on how the relationship between Siam and Great Britain should continue. The content of the treaty covers three main topics: i) English people could buy land after renting it for ten years within the distance of a 24-hour journey from Bangkok ii) Siamese government had to acknowledge the jurisdiction of British courts beyond the jurisdiction of Siamese courts for individuals under the authority of the British Empire, and iii) The trade did not need to be done through the Treasury of Siam. The second topic received criticisms from the public as it was deemed the loss of sovereignty in judicial matters (Trisadikoon 2021).

This treaty transformed the economy of Siam from a subsistence economy to a trade-led economy with huge demands because the last topic of the treaty enabled direct trade between businesses in Siam and Great Britain. Farmers expanded their agricultural land as rice became the main exported commodity (Trisadikoon 2021). Many canals, roads, and commercial buildings were built. Mint business was established to replace hand-made coins with machine-made ones. The image of Siam changed to be more open as Chao Phraya river, the

main river of Bangkok, was full of ships. With the Bowring Treaty being a model treaty, other western countries repeated similar negotiating patterns resulting in 12 additional treaties afterwards. The Bowring treaty was, therefore, considered a key to open up Siam. In the eyes of the leaders of Siam, however, the Bowring Treaty caused a profound structural change, especially in terms of tax collection. Despite the economic prosperity, fewer taxes could be collected. This diverted tax collection to other commodities, such as opium. During his stay, Sir John Bowring wrote two books called *The Kingdom and People of Siam*. The books reflected the way of living of Siamese and introduced Siam to the wider world. Thanks to this successful negotiation and adaptation, Siam was the only country in the region that did not end up being colonized. Full text of the Bowring Treaty can be downloaded from Wikisource (https://en.wikisource.org/wiki/Treaty_of_friendship_and_commerce_between_Great_Britain_and_Siam).

2.3.2. The Burney Treaty (1826)

A Thai duplicate of the Burney Treaty

([https://commons.wikimedia.org/wiki/File:Burney_Treaty_\(Thai_Duplicate\)_011.jpg#mw-jump-to-license](https://commons.wikimedia.org/wiki/File:Burney_Treaty_(Thai_Duplicate)_011.jpg#mw-jump-to-license))

The Burney Treaty came before the Bowring Treaty and was deemed unsuccessful in terms of commercial negotiation for Great Britain. The main objective of the Burney Treaty was actually to solidify Siam's alliance against Burma (Burney Treaty 2023).

2.3.3. The Roberts Treaty (1833)

The Siamese-American Treaty of Amity and Commerce, also known as the Roberts Treaty of 1833, was the first treaty between the United States and an Asian nation (Roberts Treaty 2022). Signed on March 20, 1833, and ratified on April 14, 1836, it established peaceful relations and commerce between the two states. Negotiated by Edmund Roberts, the treaty provided for perpetual peace, free trade, and relief for US citizens in cases of shipwreck. The treaty granted favorable terms to Americans compared to the British treaty of 1826. It was modified by subsequent agreements, including the Harris Treaty of 1856 and an exchange of notes in 1867. The 1833 treaty was replaced by subsequent treaties in 1921, 1938, and 1968, with the latter remaining in force today. Full text of the Roberts Treaty can be downloaded from Wikisource (https://en.wikisource.org/wiki/Treaty_of_Amity_and_Commerce_between_Siam_and_the_United_States,_1833).

3. Data and Methodology

3.1. Corpus creation

Three separate corpora are built for each treaty as the datasets for the analysis. The Bowring and the Roberts Treaties are downloaded from the Wikisource website, and the Burney Treaty is digitized. The Burney Treaty is first photographed with an iPhone 14 ProMax camera with the zoom level of no less than 1x to maximize picture resolution. Mode of photographing is automatically adjusted to text. A proper amount of light is ensured to avoid degraded image quality. After that, the photographs are uploaded into Transkribus (Kahle et al. 2017) (<https://www.transkribus.org/>), an AI-powered image-to-text tool. Transkribus is chosen as a digitization tool for this project because of its versatile features and enhanceable model in handling historical texts. The texts are then exported from Transkribus while the images of the Treaty are kept for possible investigation in the future. The text corpora of the three treaties, as well as the images, are stored on a local device and on the university's OneDrive as a back up.

3.2. Curation rationale

The three treaties, the Burney Treaty, the Bowring Treaty, the Roberts Treaty, are selected for this project due to their historical significance, timespans, and geopolitical background. The Bowring Treaty marked the pivotal point of Siam towards a more open outlook, caused fundamental changes in societal structure, and shaped the landscape of the country until now. To examine the change of linguistic phenomenon over time, the other two relatable treaties, the Burney Treaty signed before and the Roberts Treaty coming after, are chosen. This stratification results in three temporally aligning treaties that also differ in terms of main objectives and partner countries. Lastly, these treaties are written in the background setting during the expansion of the Western powers. This power dynamics is hypothesized to be reflected on the linguistic property, modality to be precise, in the treaty texts.

3.3. Methods and tools

3.3.1. SpaCy parser

SpaCy (Honnibal & Montani 2017) was developed in 2015. It is a state-of-art text parser that enables a simple yet efficient extraction process of linguistic structures. Relying on an arc-eager transition-based system, spaCy's dependency parsing algorithm uses parsing transitions to draw a dependency tree from an input sentence. The transformer architecture in its currently largest language model *en_core_web_trf* provides high-accuracy dependency parsing, which is suitable for analyzing complex and lengthy sentences, such as the diplomatic treaties in this project.

After the process of treaty digitization and corpus compilation, the treaty texts are parsed with spaCy using the dependency tag "aux" (as shown below) to extract a modal verb phrase (modal verb + infinitive verb). A set of nine major modal verbs (will, would, can, could, shall, should, may, might, must) are used as the keywords to identify modal verbs.

Sub-corpora of modal verb texts are generated, and the frequencies of modal verbs are counted. The modal verbs are categorized based on Someya’s primary, secondary, and tertiary functions using semantic functions. The sampled texts are examined to ensure categorisation accuracy. The frequencies of modal verb pairs are then used to calculate O/E, t-score, and p-value to determine the significance of the occurrence.

3.3.2. Statistical scores

O/E score is the division of an observed frequency by an expected frequency. These two types of frequencies can be derived using a contingency table as demonstrated below:

Aux_Verb_Pairs	Observed frequency of Aux_V_Pairs	Observed frequency of Aux	Observed frequency of Verb	Total
must_indicate	4	4	5	13
should_invoke	4	9	11	24
Total	8	13	16	37

$$E(x) = \frac{B * C}{D}$$

A = Observed frequency
 B = Sum of the row
 C = Sum of the column
 D = Total occurrences

Figure 1: Expected Frequency Calculation Formula Using Contingency Table

In the contingency table with made-up numbers, the expected frequency E(x) of the auxiliary-verb pair is calculated by multiplying the sum of the row (13) with the sum of the column (8) and dividing with total occurrences (37), which is 2.81. To read the result, the expected frequency of 2.81 is compared with its raw (or observed) frequency of 4. When the expected frequency is less than the observed frequency, it means that this verb pair is overrepresented. In other words, the occurrence is higher than expected.

The expected and observed frequencies, then, are used to calculate O/E score and t-score. O/E score is the division of observed frequencies with expected frequencies (4/2.81=1.42). The higher the O/E score, thus, the more overrepresented a verb pair. T-score is a measure used in hypothesis testing. To calculate a t-score, the subtraction of observed frequency with an expected frequency (4-2.81=1.19) is divided by the square root of an expected frequency ($\sqrt{2.81} \approx 1.68$), which is around 0.71. The calculation formula of t-score is shown below.

$$t = \frac{\text{Observed freq.} - \text{Expected freq.}}{\sqrt{\text{Expected freq.}}}$$

The more positively or negatively extreme the t-score, the more significant the occurrence. A

deeper interpretation of t-scores usually involves p-value. P-value represents the probability of observing a t-score in the extreme upper-or-lower tails of t-distribution. Given a t-score and a degree of freedom (df), p-value can be identified in the t-distribution table or, in this study, in Python. A degree of freedom is a number of possibilities (or variations) minus one, which in this case, is a number of auxiliary-verb-pair variations minus one ($1,054-1=1,053$). When a p-value is less than the chosen significance level, typically 0.05, the null hypothesis can be rejected, meaning the occurrence of an auxiliary-verb pair is significant and not by chance. In this example, the p-value is more than 0.05 at around 0.47 ($p>0.05$), so the auxiliary-verb pair does not occur exclusively.

3.4. Tableau

The frequencies of modal verbs are compared between the three treaties from three periods, and the semantic shift is examined in terms of epistemic and deontic senses and visualized in Tableau.

4. Data Availability

Code for text parsing and processing, together with the corpora and full project paper, is made available on Zenodo (<https://zenodo.org/>), a platform for sharing academic work under the principle of Open Science.

Critical Evaluation

This project employs several digital tools, namely Transkribus and spaCy. While there are obvious benefits in processing and analyzing the datasets, each tool comes with limitations that can or cannot be mitigated. Transkribus inherits the common erroneous nature of OCR tools regarding the accuracy of the digitized texts. As this limitation has been widely mentioned in many digital history projects, scholars attempt to find ways to minimize the mistakes to achieve more reliable results. For spaCy text parser, its main advantages are the simplicity of use with robust algorithms. Although complex configurations are needed for some purposes, a deep analysis, as well as comprehensive and insightful results, can be achieved through a simple pipeline. A smaller language model equipped in spaCy, while offering time and resource efficiency, may produce incorrect parsing results. Lastly, language style of diplomatic treaties is considered a caveat of this project when comparing the results with relevant studies conducted on everyday natural language.

Transkribus

Although digital tools and methods have vastly developed and taken a pivotal role in historical research during the past decades, countless studies that utilize digitized materials as datasets have suffered the erroneous nature of the Optical Character Recognition (OCR) tools leading to inaccurate search results and unreliable analysis. This concern is addressed in this project by manually correcting the texts and retraining the model, a unique enhancement feature that Transkribus offers, to make text recognition more accurate. This iterative correction process and continuous development of Transkribus are explained in detail in the paper of Muehlberger and team (2019).

While some studies mainly talk about OCR errors, including Cordell's "Taking Dirty OCR Seriously" (2017), and Jarlbrink and Snickars' "Cultural heritage as digital noise" (2017), others only briefly discuss this issue under the main topics of interest. At the same time, many scholars have proposed various measures to handle the challenges associated with OCR tools. Some of the popular solutions include the examination of metadata and digitization process and management (Hauswedell et al. 2020; Edelstein 2017; Cordell 2017; Jensen 2021; Owens & Padilla 2021), reliance on phrases or semantic features rather than exact word search, namely the creation of synonym list (Jensen 2021), the use of related search and weighted search (Huistra & Mellink 2016), and the use of fuzzy search (Prescott 2018), reliance more on the contextual historical knowledge in the interpretation and analysis in addition to OCR

generated texts (Putnam 2016; Paju & Hannu 2023), manual correction and verification (Ahnert & Sebastian 2019; Huistra & Mellink 2016; Daems 2019; Keck et al. 2022; Paju & Hannu 2023), and the use of software algorithms to detect and correct the errors (Guldi & Armitage 2014). With the rapid development of neural-based machine learning algorithms whether embedded with the OCR tools or employed as a post-process of texts, the optimum goal of high-accuracy digitized materials should not be far beyond.

In this project, OCR tool, Transkribus, is employed to transform the images of the Burney Treaty to texts. The tool makes it possible to perform linguistic analysis on the treaty that otherwise would not be possible to achieve with the physical or photographed treaty. The limitations of the OCR tools are recognized and managed by various methods mentioned in the previous paragraph, especially manual correction and verification. Since the treaty texts are not long, the errors can be manually edited, and put back to Transkribus to re-train the text recognition model for future use.

SpaCy parser

SpaCy parser allows for the extraction of various syntactic structures of modal verbs, such as passive voice modal verbs (shall be paid, shall be made), as well as a wider window of analysis covering subjects and verbs. This can be achieved through the use of additional tags, namely “auxpass” and “nsubjpass”, offering more comprehensive interpretations. With the parsed texts illustrated below, examples include criminal offenders *will* be punished, the wreck *shall* be taken care of, persons *shall* be set at liberty, the new Treaty *should* be specified, Paddy *may* be exported, a dearth *should* be apprehended, and all traders *may* cross. This benefit will hugely open the study for wider exploratory possibilities with more findings waiting to be discovered.

On the other hand, spaCy comes with some limitations. First, spaCy parser cannot recognize other semantically similar forms of modality. Apart from modal verbs, modality can be exhibited through other lexical mechanisms, such as will be *allowed* to, *are at liberty* to, and it is *necessary* to. This challenge may not be entirely addressed systematically with spaCy but can be mitigated by including the list of lexical variations that convey modality in the extraction code.

Second, it is cumbersome to extract complex syntactic structure like compound subjects or compound verbs using only “aux” dependency tag; for instance, “Gold and Silver in bars or ingots, and Gold Leaf, *may* be imported free”, “The landing, shipment, or transhipment of goods *may* be carried on”, “the Siamese may prohibit the Trade in Rice, and may enforce the prohibition” and “All cargo landed or shipped shall be examined and passed”. This requires more complex configurations to the extraction code involving additional dependency and part-of-speech tags, not to mention tedious manual process in the frequency count as these compound structures need to be segregated; for example, the compound verb in “the Siamese may prohibit the Trade in Rice, and may enforce the prohibition” will result in two subject-verb pairs “the Siamese may prohibit” and “the Siamese may enforce”. A more chaotic scenario would be a compound subject and a compound verb in a single expression, namely “British subjects, their persons, houses, premises, lands, ships, or property of any kind, *shall* not be seized, injured, or in any way interfered with by the Siamese.” Nevertheless, if successfully done, the code will give more accurate results leading to a more meaningful and enriched analysis.

Third, spaCy cannot recognize referential dependencies beyond a sentence level. This mainly involves the identification of the reference of a pronoun or a definitive phrase that refers to an entity located in a different sentence. Take the following texts as example where “the deceased” refers to “a British subject dying in Siam” in the first text and “They” refers to “The said Royal Commissioners”:

In the event of a British subject dying in Siam, and leaving houses, lands, or other property, his relations, or those persons who are heirs according to English law, shall receive possession of the said property; and the British Consul, or some one appointed by the British Consul, may proceed at once to take charge of the said property on their account. If the deceased should owe money, the Consul shall liquidate his debts as far as the estate of the deceased shall suffice.

The said Royal Commissioners, at the request of Mr Parkes, and in conformity with the intent of the 8th Article of the new Treaty, agree to the immediate establishment of a Custom House, under the superintendence of a High Government Functionary, for the examination of all goods landed or shipped, and the receipt of the Import and Export Duties due thereon. Th(e)y further agree that the business of the Custom House shall be conducted under the Regulations annexed to this Agreement.

Forth, even if the pronoun and its reference are within the same sentence, spaCy may not be completely accurate when there are multiple possible references for the pronoun. Take the following sentence as an example:

British subjects who may previously obtain special permission from the Siamese Authorities to export a certain quantity of Rice which they have already purchased, may do so even after the prohibition comes in force.

Even though it is clear that “they” refers to “British subjects”, SpaCy assigns “quantity” as a reference of “they” instead due to its proximity with the relative clause (relcl).

Last but not least, spaCy offers different NLP models with difference levels of performance (Available trained pipelines for English 2023) accommodating various task requirements from a small model *en_core_web_sm* opt for a fast parsing with less accuracy (90-92% for parser) to the currently largest model with transformer architecture *en_core_web_trf* returning the most accurate results (94-95% for parser) but slower processing time and higher computational resource consumption. While the performance gap is minimal, a small model can cause wrong extraction results as demonstrated below. The small model *en_core_web_sm* mistakenly tags “cargo” as a subject and “landed” as a verb whereas the transformer model *en_core_web_trf* correctly recognizes subject and verb dependency with “cargo” being a subject depending on the verb “examined” in a passive voice construction.

Parsed text by a small model, *en_core_web_sm*

Parsed text by a transformer model, *en_core_web_trf*

Although the last two issues of ambiguity constitute limitations of spaCy, they are relatively rare in the context of diplomatic treaties as the texts are originally written to convey the meanings as clearly as possible.

Language style

While modality may seem to be a suitable topic for examining historical treaties, the language use in the treaties is not completely authentic and natural as it is heavily governed by a certain diplomatic style and formality. In addition, the language style in the treaties can be different from modern English, and modal verbs may also be used differently in the 19th century. Considering the authenticity of the language use and nature of diplomatic language, the comparison of semantic shift with Millar’s findings (2009) may not be entirely accurate.

Bibliography

- Ahnert, Ruth & Sebastian E. Ahnert. 2019. Metadata, Surveillance and the Tudor State. *History Workshop Journal* 87. 27-51. <https://doi.org/10.1093/hwj/dby033>.
- Available trained pipelines for English. 2023. <https://spacy.io/models/en>. (9 May, 2024).
- Baldwin, Timothy & Villavicencio, Aline. 2002. Extracting the Unextractable: A Case Study on Verb-particles. In *COLING-02: The 6th Conference on Natural Language Learning 2002 (CoNLL-2002)*. 98-104. <https://aclanthology.org/W02-2001/>.
- Bowring Treaty. 2022. https://en.m.wikipedia.org/wiki/Bowring_Treaty. (25 April, 2024).
- Burney Treaty. 2023. https://en.m.wikipedia.org/wiki/Burney_Treaty. (25 April, 2024).
- Coates, Jennifer. 1983. *The Semantics of the Modal Auxiliaries*. London: Croom Helm.
- Cordell, Ryan. 2017. “Q i-Jtb the Raven”: Taking Dirty OCR Seriously. *Book History* (20). 188–225. <https://doi.org/10.1353/bh.2017.0006>.
- Daems, Joke. 2019. Workers of the World? A Digital Approach to Classify the International Scope of Belgian Socialist Newspapers, 1885-1940. *Journal of European Periodical Studies* 4(1). 98-114. <https://doi.org/10.21825/jeps.v4i1.10187>.
- Edelstein, Dan et al. 2017. Historical Research in a Digital Age: Reflections from the Mapping the Republic of Letters Project. *The American Historical Review* 122(2). 400-24. <https://doi.org/10.1093/ahr/122.2.400>.
- FAROSE podcast. 2022. PYMK EP39 เยาว์ริง กับสนธิสัญญาพลิกแผ่นดินสยาม และเรื่องที่ไม่อยู่ในหนังสือเรียน [Translation: Sir John Bowring and the Treaty that Transformed Siam and Stories Not Found in Textbooks]. <https://youtu.be/TpAQoEIIpss?si=Av4AGTLPIyK30ybV>. (3 May, 2024).
- Guldi, Jo & Armitage, David. 2014. *The History Manifesto*. Cambridge University Press.
- Hauswedell, Tessa, Nyhan, Julianne, Beals, H. Melody, Terras, Melissa & Bell, Emily. 2020. Of global reach yet of situated contexts: an examination of the implicit and explicit selection criteria that shape digital archives of historical newspapers. *Arch Sci* 20. 139–65. <https://doi.org/10.1007/s10502-020-09332-1>.
- Honnibal, Matthew, & Montani, Ines. 2017. spaCy 2: Natural language understanding with Bloom embeddings, convolutional neural networks and incremental parsing.
- Huistra, Hieke & Mellink, Bram. 2016. Phrasing History: Selecting Sources in Digital Repositories. *Historical Methods: A Journal of Quantitative and Interdisciplinary History* 49(4). 220–29. 10.1080/01615440.2016.1205964.

- Jarlbrink, Johan & Snickars, Pelle. 2017. Cultural heritage as digital noise : nineteenth century newspapers in the digital archive. *Journal of Documentation* 73(6). 1228-43.
<https://doi.org/10.1108/JD-09-2016-0106>.
- Jensen, H. Strandgaard. 2021. Digital Archival Literacy for (All) Historians. *Media History* 27(2). 251-65. 10.1080/13688804.2020.1779047.
- Kahle, Philip, Colutto, Sebastian, Hackl, Günter & Mühlberger, Günter. 2017. Transkribus - A Service Platform for Transcription, Recognition and Retrieval of Historical Documents. In *the 14th IAPR International Conference on Document Analysis and Recognition (ICDAR)*. 19-24. 10.1109/ICDAR.2017.307.
- Keck, Jana, Oiva, Mila & Fyfe, Paul. 2022. Lajos Kossuth and the Transnational News: A Computational and Multilingual Approach to Digitized Newspaper Collections. *Media History*. 1-18. <https://doi.org/10.1080/13688804.2022.2146905>.
- Leech, Geoffrey. 2003. Modals on the move: The English modal auxiliaries 1961–1992. In Facchinetti, Roberta, Palmer, Frank & Krug, Manfred (eds.), *Modality in Contemporary English*. 223–240. Berlin/New York: Mouton de Gruyter.
- Lehmann, Hans M. & Schneider, Gerold. 2009. Parser-based analysis of syntax-lexis interactions. In *Corpora: Pragmatics and Discourse*. 477–502.
https://doi.org/10.1163/9789042029101_024.
- Masavisut, Nitaya, Sukwiwat, Mayuri & Wongmontha, Seri. 1986. The power of the English language in Thai media. *World Englishes* 5. 197-207.
<https://doi.org/10.1111/j.1467-971X.1986.tb00726.x>.
- MacKinlay, Andrew, Martinez, David & Baldwin Timothy. 2011. A parser-based approach to detecting modification of biomedical events. In *Proceedings of the ACM fifth international workshop on Data and text mining in biomedical informatics*.
<https://doi.org/10.1145/2064696.2064707>.
- Meethong, Dhitiditiphong, Kumlaed, Nuttida, Thunkarn, Piyaporn, Aem-ot, Kanyarat & Rattanakulditok, Piyathida. 2020. The Bowring Treaty with the Economic Impact of Thailand Buddhist Era 2398 [สนธิสัญญาเบาว์ริงกับผลกระทบทางเศรษฐกิจของประเทศไทย พุทธศักราช 2398]. Nakhon Pathom Rajabhat University.
<https://publication.npru.ac.th/handle/123456789/1111>.
- Millar, Neil. 2009. Modal Verbs in TIME: Frequency Changes 1923-2006. *International Journal of Corpus Linguistics* 14(2). 191-220.
- Muehlberger, Guenter, Seaward, Louise, Terras, Melissa, Ares Oliveira, Sofia, Bosch, Vicente, Bryan, Maximilian, Colutto, Sebastian, Déjean, Hervé, Diem, Markus, Fiel,

- Stefan, Gatos, Basilis, Greinöcker, Albert, Grüning, Tobias, Hackl, Guenter, Haukkovaara, Vili, Heyer, Gerhard, Hirvonen, Lauri, Hodel, Tobias, Jokinen, Matti, Kahle, Philip, Kallio, Mario, Kaplan, Frederic, Kleber, Florian, Labahn, Roger, Lang, Eva Maria, Laube, Sören, Leifert, Gundram, Louloudis, Georgios, McNicholl, Rory, Meunier, Jean-Luc, Michael, Johannes, Mühlbauer, Elena, Philipp, Nathanael, Pratikakis, Ioannis, Puigcerver Pérez, Joan, Putz, Hannelore, Retsinas, George, Romero, Verónica, Sablatnig, Robert, Sánchez, Joan Andreu, Schofield, Philip, Sfikas, Giorgos, Sieber, Christian, Stamatopoulos, Nikolaos, Strauß, Tobias, Terbul, Tamara, Toselli, Alejandro Héctor, Ulreich, Berthold, Villegas, Mauricio, Vidal, Enrique, Walcher, Johanna, Weidemann, Max, Wurster, Herbert, Zagoris, Konstantinos. 2019. Transforming scholarship in the archives through handwritten text recognition: Transkribus as a case study. *Journal of Documentation* 75(5). 954-76. <https://doi.org/10.1108/JD-07-2018-0114>.
- Owens, Trevor, Padilla, Thomas. 2021. Digital sources and digital archives: historical evidence in the digital age. *Int J Digit Humanities* 1. 325-41. <https://doi.org/10.1007/s42803-020-00028-7>.
- Paju, Petri & Hannu Salmi. 2023. Medical and Miraculous Cures on Sale: Newspapers, advertisements and readers between fact and fantasy. In Patrick Lundell et al. 2023. *Information Flows across the Baltic Sea: Towards a Computational Approach to Media History (Föreningen mediehistoriskt arkiv)*. 183-214. <https://doi.org/10.54292/s6au8axqht>.
- Prescott, Andrew. 2018. Chapter 2 Searching for Dr. Johnson: The Digitisation of the Burney Newspaper Collection. In *Travelling Chronicles*. Leiden, The Netherlands: Brill. https://doi.org/10.1163/9789004362871_004.
- Putnam, Lara. 2016. The Transnational and the Text-Searchable: Digitized Sources and the Shadows They Cast. *The American Historical Review* 121(2). 377-402. <https://doi.org/10.1093/ahr/121.2.377>.
- Rayson, Paul, Archer, Dawn, Baron, Alistair, Culpeper, Jonathan & Smith, Nicholas. 2007. *Tagging the Bard: Evaluating the accuracy of a modern POS tagger on Early Modern English corpora*.
- Rinaldi, Fabio, Schneider, Gerold, Kaljurand, Kaarel, Hess, Michael, Andronis, Christos, Konstandi, Ourania & Persidis, Andreas. 2007. Mining of relations between proteins over biomedical scientific literature using a deep-linguistic approach. *Artificial Intelligence in Medicine* 39(2). 127-36. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.artmed.2006.08.005>.

Robert Treaty. 2022.

https://en.m.wikipedia.org/wiki/Siamese%E2%80%93American_Treaty_of_Amity_and_Commerce. (3 May, 2024).

Schneider, Gerold & Hundt, Marianne. 2009. Using a parser as a heuristic tool for the description of New Englishes. In *the Fifth Corpus Linguistics Conference*. Liverpool, UK.

Schneider, Gerold. 2012. *Adapting a parser to historical English*. Helsinki: University of Helsinki. <https://varieng.helsinki.fi/series/volumes/10/schneider/>.

Seretan, Violeta & Wehrli, Eric. 2006. Accurate Collocation Extraction Using a Multilingual Parser. In *Proceedings of the 21st International Conference on Computational Linguistics and 44th Annual Meeting of the Association for Computational Linguistics*, Sydney, Australia. 953–960. <https://aclanthology.org/P06-1120>.

Smith, Nucharee N. & Smith, Robert B. 2019. Has Thailand learnt any Lessons from the Bowring Treaty and the Treaty of Amity?. *Athens JL* 5. 405-17. https://heinonline.org/HOL/P?h=hein_journals/atnsj2019&i=437.

Sohn, Sunghwan, Wu, Stephen, Chute, Christopher G. 2012. Dependency Parser-based Negation Detection in Clinical Narratives. *AMIA Jt Summits Transl Sci Proc* 2012. 1-8. <https://www.ncbi.nlm.nih.gov/pmc/articles/PMC3392064/>.

Someya, Yasumasa. 2010. Modal verbs and their semantic functions in business English. In *Aoyama journal of business* 44(3). 1-37.

Terwiel, Barend J. 1991. *The Bowring Treaty: Imperialism and the indigenous perspective*. The Australian National University. https://thesiamsociety.org/wp-content/uploads/1991/03/JSS_079_2f_Terwiel_Bowring_Treaty.pdf.

Trisadikoon, Khemmapat. 2021. ผลกระทบของสนธิสัญญาเบาว์ริงในทางเศรษฐกิจของสยาม [Translation: The economic impact of the Bowring Treaty on Siam]. Pridi Banomyong Institute. <https://pridi.or.th/th/content/2021/07/774>. (3 May, 2024).

Trisadikoon, Khemmapat. 2021. สนธิสัญญาเบาว์ริง: หนังสือสัญญาที่ว่าด้วยเรื่องระหว่างราชอาณาจักรสยามกับสหราชอาณาจักร [Translation: Bowring Treaty: A treaty document concerning the affairs between the Kingdom of Siam and the British Empire]. Pridi Banomyong Institute. <https://pridi.or.th/th/content/2021/07/777>. (3 May, 2024).